

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL EMULGEL ON WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

**Komal Rahevar*, Dhara Patel, Runika Utekar, Vaishali Shrivastav, Sohan Patel,
Mukesh Patel, Satyajit Sahoo**

*Pioneer Pharmacy College, Department of Pharmaceutics, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 10 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17878762>

*Corresponding Author

Komal Rahevar

Pioneer Pharmacy College,
Department of Pharmaceutics,
Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

How to cite this Article: Komal Rahevar*, Dhara Patel, Runika Utekar, Vaishali Shrivastav, Sohan Patel, Mukesh Patel, Satyajit Sahoo (2025). Formulation And Evaluation Of Polyherbal Emulgel On Wound Healing Activity. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1793–1802. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Emulgel is a topical preparation. Prepared by the combination of emulsion and gel. Emulgels consist of curcumin, ascorbic acid, and salicylic acid. Emulgel is considered one of the most important topical delivery systems because it consists of two release control systems, i.e., gel and emulsion. The primary intention of this new topical delivery system is to deliver hydrophobic drugs into systemic circulation through the skin. Emulgel formulations were prepared using Carbopol 934 as a gelling agent. The main purpose of this research was to design, formulate, and evaluate a topical emulgel by using the high molecular weight water-soluble polymer Carbopol 934. This carbopol possesses very high viscosity, transparency, and film-forming properties at low concentrations and is reported to be useful in the formation of gel with an objective to increase transparency and Spreadability. All the prepared emulgel showed acceptable physical properties concerning colour,

consistency, spreadability, and pH value. The influence of the type of gelling agent on the drug release from the prepared emulgel was investigated, and Carbopol 934 showed good results in physical evaluation parameters. From the drug evaluation studies, the F5 formulation showed good clarity, physical appearance, and viscosity of 2250 cps. Stability studies showed that the physical appearance and anti-inflammatory activity of all the prepared emulgels remained unchanged upon storage for 1 month. It was finally concluded that the formulation F5 with 1% w/w Carbopol 934 was found to be a more promising

formulation as it shows better physicochemical characteristics and anti-inflammatory activity compared to other formulations.

KEYWORD: Emulgel, Ascorbic acid, Salicylic acid, Curcumin, Wound healing, Topical drug delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Topical drug administration is a localised drug delivery system through various routes, such as ophthalmic, rectal, vaginal, and skin, anywhere in the body. Topical preparations are chiefly utilised topically to achieve localised effects at the site of their application.^[1] The wound may be defined as the breaking or loss of anatomical and cellular or functional connections of living tissue. It is an unavoidable part of human life that is caused by chemical, physical, thermal, immunological, or microbial damage to the tissue. Emulgel is defined as biphasic systems comprising a polar internal phase (emulsion) within an aqueous gel base. The emulgel system is a novel approach for drug delivery applications, especially for hydrophobic drugs. The preparation of emulgel comprises simple and short steps, which increase the feasibility of the production. The rheological properties and the breakdown behaviour of gels filled with emulsion droplets can be varied by changing the interactions between oil droplets and gel matrix, the oil content, and the oil droplet size. The selection of polymer for preparing gel is normally based on the character of the external phase. Emulgels like better stability, better loading capacity, production feasibility, low preparation cost, no intensive sonication, controlled release, avoidance of first-pass metabolism, avoidance of gastrointestinal incompatibility, being more selective to a specific site, improving patient compliance and suitability for self-medication, Hydrophobic drugs can be easily incorporated into gels using w/o/w emulsions. The major drawback of this gel over many advantages is in the delivery of hydrophobic drugs. So, to overcome this drawback, an emulsion-based approach is being used so that even a hydrophobic therapeutic moiety can enjoy the unique properties of gels. The use of Emulgel can be expanded in analgesics, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, anti-fungal, anti-acne drugs, and various cosmetic formulations.^{[2][3]} The aim of the present research work was to investigate the potential of polyherbal emulgel in enhancing the topical delivery of curcumin, salicylic acid, and ascorbic acid. The major objective behind this formulation is the delivery of hydrophobic drugs to systemic circulation via skin.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

MATERIALS

Curcumin, ascorbic acid, salicylic acid, carbopol 934, liquid paraffin, and propylene glycol were provided as free samples by Sulab Lab, and HPMC K15M and HPMC K100M were procured by ChemDyes.

METHOD

The λ_{\max} value of ascorbic acid, salicylic acid, and curcumin was found to be 265 nm, 295 nm, and 230 nm by using a UV spectrophotometer. Three UV spectrophotometric methods have been developed: the simultaneous equation method.^[12] In method I, three wavelengths 230, 265, and 295 nm were selected, which are the λ_{\max} of three drugs for the development of the simultaneous equations. The absorbances of curcumin, ascorbic acid, and salicylic acid were measured, and the absorptivity values E (1%, 1 cm) were determined at all three selected wavelengths. The concentrations of three drugs in the mixture can be calculated using the following equation:

Simultaneous Equation

$$C_{\text{curcumin}} = \frac{A_1(ay_2az_3 - az_2ay_3) - ay_1(A_2az_3 - az_2A_3) + az_1(A_2ay_3 - ay_2A_3)}{ax_1(ay_2az_3 - az_2ay_3) - ay_1(ax_2az_3 - az_2ax_3) + az_1(ax_2ay_3 - ay_2ax_3)} \dots\dots\dots(1),$$

$$C_{\text{Ascorbic acid}} = \frac{(ax_1(A_2az_3 - az_2A_3) - A_1(ax_2az_3 - az_2ax_3) + az_1(ax_2A_3 - A_2ax_3))}{ax_1(ay_2az_3 - az_2ay_3) - ay_1(ax_2az_3 - az_2ax_3) + az_1(ax_2ay_3 - ay_2ax_3)} \dots\dots\dots(2),$$

$$C_{\text{Salicylic acid}} = \frac{(ax_1(ay_2A_3 - A_2ay_3) - ay_1(ax_2A_3 - A_2ax_3) + A_1(ax_2ay_3 - ay_2ax_3))}{ax_1(ay_2az_3 - az_2ay_3) - ay_1(ax_2az_3 - az_2ax_3) + az_1(ax_2ay_3 - ay_2ax_3)} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Preparation of Gel

The quantity of Carbopol 934 was weighed and mixed homogenously with distilled water at 65–70 °C by using a magnetic stirrer; the stirring speed was 1000 ± 200 RPM for 10 min to form a smooth dispersion. The preparation is allowed to stand, permitting entrapped air to separate. Then the pH was adjusted to 6-6.5 by using triethanolamine.^[3]

Preparation of Emulsion

The aqueous phase of the emulsion was prepared by dissolving in Tween 80 in distilled water, and further salicylic acid was added to the phase. Methyl paraben was dissolved in propylene glycol and mixed with aqueous phase. The oil phase of the emulsion was prepared

by dissolving Span 80 in light liquid paraffin and peppermint oil also Ascorbic acid was also mixed in oil phase.^[4]

Preparation of Emulgel

The Emulsion was incorporated into gel base in a 1:1 ratio under continuous mixing using a mechanical stirrer at 5000-6000 RPM for 10-20 minutes to obtained emulgel. The drug (Curcumin, Ascorbic acid, Salicylic acid) was dissolved in methanol, and they were mixed with the aqueous phase. The aqueous phase and oil phase were heated in a water bath at 70⁰ C separately. Oil phase was added dropwise to the aqueous phase with continuous stirring using a homogeniser for 10 min, then cooled to room temperature. At the end, the Gel and Emulsion portion were mixed with moderately stirring to prepare Emulgel.^[4]

Table No. 2: Formulation Table of Emulgel.

Ingredients(%w/w)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Tween80	0.3	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Span80	0.45	0.45	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Methyl Paraben	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Liquid Paraffin	3.75	3.75	7.50	7.50	7.50	3.75	3.75	3.75	3.75
Propylene glycol	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	1
Methanol	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Ascorbic Acid	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Salicylic Acid	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Curcumin	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Carbopol 934	1	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.7	-	-	-	-
Hpmck15	-	-	-	-	-	2	2.5	-	-
Hpmck100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2.5

EVALUATION OF EMULGEL OPTIMIZED BATCH F1 to F9

Physical examination

The colour of the formulation was checked against a white and a black background. The consistency of emulgel was checked by applying on the skin. The odour of emulgel was checked by mixing it in water and by smelling it.^[5]

pH

It is determined by using a digital pH meter (Digital pH meter 115 pm). 1% solution of Emulgel was prepared and subjected to measuring pH with a digital pH meter.^[5]

Viscosity

The rheological property of the Emulgel sample was determined by using a Brookfield viscometer. The viscosities of the formulations ranged from 36,000 to 51,000 cps.

Spreadability

A lower glass slide was fixed on this block. An excess of prepared emulgel (1gm) was placed on a ground slide. Emulgel formulation was then sandwiched between the slide and another glass slide having the dimensions of fixed ground slide and provided by hook. Weight of 100gm was placed on top of two slides for 5 min to expel air and to provide uniform film of gel between the slide. Excess of emulgel was scrapped off from the edges. Upper slide was then subjected to pull 20g weight with the help of string attached to hook and the time required by upper slide to cover distance.^[6]

Shorter interval indicated better spreadability.

Spreadability (S) was calculated as follow:

$$S=M.L/T$$

S= spreadability. M= weight tied to upper slide. L= length of glass slide. T= time taken to separate the slides completely.

Drug Content

A spectrophotometer is used to determine the drug concentration in the emulsion. The drug content of an emulsion is determined by sonicating a known amount of emulsion in a solvent (methanol). In a UV/VIS spectrophotometer, absorbance is measured after appropriate dilution. Drug content in Emulgel was measured by dissolving 1gm of Emulgel in 100ml of solvent (a mixture of ethanol). After filter the solution to obtain a clear solution and subjected to spectrophotometric analysis after suitable dilution.^[3,4]

Stability study

Emulgel was packed in aluminium collapsible tubes (5gm) and subjected to a stability study for 1 month. Samples are withdrawn at each 10days as per ICH guidelines and analysed for their physical appearance, pH, drug content, drug release profile, etc.^[7]

Extrudability

It is a usual empirical test to measure the force required to extrude the material from a tube. The method applied for the determination of applied shear in the region of the rheogram

corresponding to a shear rate exceeding the yield value and exhibiting consequent plug flow. In the present study, the method adopted for evaluating emulgel formulation for extrudability is based upon the quantity in percentage of emulgel and emulgel extruded from lacquered aluminium collapsible tube on application of weight in grams required to extrude at least 0.5cm ribbon of emulgel in a second. More quantity extruded is better extrudability. The measurement of extrudability is then calculated by using the following formula.^[8]

$$\text{Extrudability} = \text{Applied weight to extrude emulgel from tube (in gm)}/\text{Area (in cm}^2\text{)}$$

In Vitro Drug Release

Study Franz diffusion cell (with an effective diffusion area of 3.14 cm² and a 15.5 ml cell volume) was used for the drug release studies. Gelified Emulsion (500 mg) was applied evenly to the surface of the egg membrane, which was clamped between the donor and the receptor chamber of diffusion cell. The receptor chamber was filled with freshly prepared PBS (pH 7.4) solution to solubilize the drug. The receptor chamber was stirred by a magnetic stirrer. The samples (1.0 ml aliquots) were collected at suitable time intervals. Samples were analysed for drug content by UV/VIS = visible spectrophotometer after appropriate dilutions. The cumulative amount of drug released across the egg membrane was determined as a function of time.^[9,10]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

where, C curcumin, C Ascorbic acid and C Salicylic acid are the conc. of Curcumin, Ascorbic acid and Salicylic acid respectively in mixture and in sample solutions. A1, A2 and A3 are the absorbances of sample at 230, 265 & 295 nm, ax1, ax2 and ax3 are the absorptivity of Curcumin at 230, 265 and 295nm, ay1, ay2 and ay3 are the absorptivity of Ascorbic Acid at 265, 295 & 230 nm, az1, az2 and az3 are the absorptivity of Salicylic Acid 295, 265 and 230nm, respectively.^[11]

Drug Name	Weight (gm)	Obtained Drug	Drug Content
Salicylic Acid	0.2g	0.195g	97.5%
Curcumin	0.05g	0.049g	98%
Ascorbic Acid	0.3g	0.305g	101.66%

Table no: 3 Physical Examination.

Sr.no	Formulation code	colour	Phase separation	Homogeneity	Consistency
1	F1	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
2	F2	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
3	F3	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
4	F4	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
5	F5	Pale yellow	None	Excellent	+++
6	F6	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
7	F7	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
8	F8	Pale yellow	None	Good	++
9	F9	Pale yellow	None	Good	++

STABILITY STUDIES FOR F5 (1.7% Carbopol 934)

The stability study of Emulgel is performed according to International Council on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. Stability study for the best formulation was done as per the procedure. The gel was both physically and chemically stable at 4-50c, Room temperature and 37±50c. The Emulgel formulations are packed in collapsible tubes made up of aluminium. Then these tubes are stored at different temperatures and relative humidity.

Time (HR)	CPR		
	F3	F4	F5
0	0	0	0
0.5hr	15.12	15.65	16.87
1hr	25.56	31.12	35.5
2hr	55.79	52.25	65.58
3hr	63.2	68.01	70.25
4hr	73.25	75.45	82.25

In vitro drug release study

CONCLUSION

Emulgel are easily removable, spreadable, thixotropic, greaseless, have a pleasing appearance, emollient, long shelf life, and transparent. In the present era, the Emulgel are being used for the delivery of many drugs like analgesics, anti-inflammatory, antiacne and

anti-fungal. Hence, it is of great pharmacological importance and is relatively free of side effects. In coming years, the topical drug delivery will be used extensively to improve better patient compliance. In present study curcumin, ascorbic acid and salicylic acid combination of drug used as Topical Emulgel were prepared by using polymers such as Carbopol 934, and liquid paraffin and tween 80 used as an emulsifier, propylene glycol as a penetration enhancer. In this study all the formulations were subjected to various evaluation parameters such as physical appearance, PH evaluation, spreadability, Rheological studies, drug content and were found to be within the limits among all the formulations formulated topical emulgel containing Carbopol 934 as a polymer and liquid paraffin as an oil we can conclude that F5 formulation was the best formulations.

REFERENCES

1. Kshirsagar, N. A. "Drug delivery systems." *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 2000; 32.4: 54-61.
2. Patil, Sakshi Sanjay, Pallavi Arjun Patil, and Rutuja R. Shah. "Overview on Emulgel and their marketed Formulations." 2023; 330-332.
3. Raju, K., et al. "Formulation and evaluation of ornidazole topical emulgel." 2019; *WJPPS* 8.07: 1179-1197.
4. Chauhan, Shikha Baghel. "Formulation and Evaluation of Emulgel for the treatment of Acne." *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 2020; 13.8: 3598-3602.
5. Khan, Barkat Ali, et al. "Formulation and evaluation of Ocimum basilicum-based emulgel for wound healing using animal model." *Saudi pharmaceutical journal*, 2020; 28.12: 1842-1850.
6. Mutimer, Margaret N., et al. "Modern ointment base technology II. Comparative evaluation of bases." *Journal of the American Pharmaceutical Association* 1956; 45.4: 212-218.
7. Jain, Ankur, et al. "Development of antifungal emulsion based gel for topical fungal infection (s)." 2011; *IJPRD* 2.12: 18-22.
8. Gupta, G. D., and R. S. Gaud. "Release rate of nimesulide from different gellants." *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 1999; 61: 227-230.
9. Jain, Narendra Kumar, ed. *Progress in controlled and novel drug delivery systems*. CBS Publishers & Distributors, 2004.

10. Lathiyare, Kumar Bandhu, Preeti K. Suresh, and Vishal Jain. "Development and in vitro characterization of piroxicam loaded emulgel for topical delivery." *Int J Pharm Pharm Res.*, 2015; 2.3: 18-32.
11. Rahman, Md Mizanur, Mohammad Mizanur Rahman Khan, and Mohammad Mazedul Hosain. "Analysis of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) contents in various fruits and vegetables by UV-spectrophotometry." *Bangladesh Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research* 2007; 42.4: 417-424.
12. Panwar, A., et al. "Emulgel: A review." *Asian J Pharm Life Sci.*, 2011; 2231: 4423.